

**PERCEPTION OF BRICK KILNS MANUFACTURERS TOWARDS THEIR
PRODUCTION – ANALYSIS WITH REFERENCE TO
MEKKIRIMANGALAM VILLAGE**

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Abstract:

A potter uses clay to create works of art. There are a wide variety of clays to choose from each with the own unique properties. The clay a potter chooses depends on what they want the finished products to look and feel like. Many different tools are used in this profession, including carving tools, modes, pottery wheels and kilns. After molding clay into a desired shape, the pottery maker places it in a kiln, a specialized oven that dries and hardens the clay. After the piece has baked in the kiln, it is removed, painted and then glazed. Basic artist ability is important and can be further developed and refined over time and practice. Creativity is also important as a professional artist must be able to constantly come up with new ideas that are interesting, appealing, and unique. Many potters are self-employed, and can usually set their own hours. They make money by selling their works to individuals via art galleries, craft fairs, and personal studio shows rooms. Some also sell their wares online. Typically, self - employed pottery makers have an art studio in which they do their work. Rural small scale sector particularly brick kilns industry plays an important role in rural economy. Hence this study, an attempt is made to analyze the Perception of Brick Kilns Manufacturers towards their Production – Analysis with Reference to Mekkirimangalam Village.

Keyword: Pottery, Profit, Artwork.

A potter or pottery maker is a craft artist who uses their artistic talent to create pots, dishes, mugs, vases and other types of artwork. Most potters create functional pieces that are meant to be put to everyday use. A potter or pottery maker of a craft artist (a craft artist is someone who uses a variety of materials and techniques to create art for sale and exhibition. They create handmade objects such as pottery, glassware, textiles or other objects that are usually designed to be functional, but sometimes the original works of art have only aesthetic value rather than a functional one.) Who uses their artistic talent to create pots, dishes, mugs, vases and other types of art works? Most potters as works of art. A potter can train for decades to become a true master of the art of making pottery; forever learning and improving their craft.

Work place of a potter

Many potters are self-employed, and can usually set their own hours. They make money by selling their works to individuals via art galleries, craft fairs, and personal studio shows rooms. Some also sell their wares online. Typically, self - employed pottery makers have an art studio in which they do their work.

Besides self-employment, there are other employment options. Many work as instructors, teaching pottery-making class and workshops in schools, colleges or private settings. Some work for various private sector industries like pottery manufacturers. Pottery makers, especially those with some types of formal education, can also work in art galleries, art museums, and art foundations.

Many craft artists teach art to others. In order to teach art in an elementary or secondary school, an individual must usually have a teaching certificate and a bachelor's degree. Teaching at a college or university level required an advanced degree in fine arts.

Types of clay

- Earthenware
- Stoneware
- Glazes

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the present study are:

- To find out the profit of the pottery industry in the study area.
- To know the gender and age of the respondents in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

Both primary and secondary data have been collected for the study. As the total number of pot makers in the study area is 40. The primary data is collected by census method. In the census method, their performance related response is arrived through oral and personal interview. Secondary data were collected from various books, newspapers, journals, magazines and websites. Collected data were analyzed by using tables.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The study covers period of five years from 2011-2012 to 2015-2016.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The following are the Limitations of the study:

- ❖ The sample size is restricted to only 40 respondents. Hence it will not represent the universal population.
- ❖ The study covers only kanjanagaram village only.

CHAPTER SCHEME

1. The First Chapter deals with Introduction.
2. The Second Chapter covers with Profile of the Study Area.
3. The Third Chapter represents with Data analysis and Interpretation.
4. The Fourth Chapter Exposes to Findings and Suggestions.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**Table .1****Gender Wise Classification of the Respondent**

Sex	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Male	29	72
Female	11	28
Total	40	100

From the above table.1 clear that the total respondents are male 72% while 28% of Female. One can infer from the above gender wise classification the male are more in number.

Table .2**Age wise**

Age group	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Below 25 years	4	10
25-35 years	9	23
35-45 years	11	27
45- above	16	40
Total	40	100

From the above table.2 shows that the respondent were choose deliberately from different age group out of 40 respondents, 40% respondents were above the age group of 45 years, 27% respondents are between 35-45 years, 23% respondents are between 25-35 years, 10% respondents are below 25 years.

Table No .3**Education Wise Classification of the Respondent**

Literacy level	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Illiterate	12	30
Primary	10	25
H.Sc	8	20
Degree	6	15
PG	3	8
Professional	1	2
Total	40	100

From the above shows that 30% of the respondent are illiterate, 45% of respondent are upto school level, 15% of respondent are graduates, 8% of the respondents are post graduate and 2% of respondents are professional degree holder.

Table .4
Profit of the Mud Pot

Year	Category of product	Profit in rupees	Trend percentage
2011-12	Mud Pot	15,200	100
2012-13		24,800	163
2013-14		25,000	101
2014-15		4,900	20
2015-16		300	6
Total			70,200

The above table .4 shows the profit of the Mud Pot from the sample respondents in the kanjanagaram village. 101% profit of the Mud Pot in the year 2013-14, 163% profit of the mud Pot in the year 2012-13, 20% profit of the Mud Pot in the year 2014-15 and lowest profit (i.e 6%) in the profit of the Mud Pot in the year 2015-16. The highest percentage of profit of the Mud Pot in the year 2012-13.

Table .5
Profit of the Mud Lamp

Year	Category of product	Profit in rupees	Trend percentage
2011-12	Mud Lamp	320	100
2012-13		800	250
2013-14		1120	140
2014-15		7100	634
2015-16		1600	23
Total			10940

The above table.5 shows the profit of the Mud Lamp from the sample respondent in the kanjanagaram village. 634% profit of the Mud lamp in the tear 2014-15, 23% profit of the mud Lamp in the year 2015-16, 140% profit of the Mud Lamp in the year 2013-14. 250% profit of the Mud lamp in the year 2012-13 and lowest profit (i.e 23%) in the year 2015-16. The highest percentage of profit of the Mud Lamp in the year 2014-15.

Table .6
Profit of the Mud Hundi

Year	Category of product	Profit in rupees	Trend percentage
2011-12	Mud Hundi	660	100
2012-13		840	127
2013-14		1190	142
2014-15		550	46
2015-16		1000	182
Total			4240

The above table.6 shows the profit of the Mud Hundi from the sample respondents in the kanjanagaram village. 142% profit of the Mud Hundi in the year 2013-14, 182% profit off the Mud Hundi in the year 2015-16, 127% profit of the Mud Hundi in the year 2012-13 and lowest profit (i.e.46%) in the year 2014-15. The highest percentage of the Mud Hundi in the year 2015-16.

FINDINGS

- The total respondents are male 72% while 28% of Female.
- 40% respondents were above the age group of 45 years.
- 30% of the respondent are illiterate.
- The highest percentage of profit of the Mud Pot in the year 2012-13.
- The highest percentage of profit of the Mud Lamp in the year 2014-15.
- The highest percentage of the Mud Hundi in the year 2015-16.

SUGGESTIONS

*** Distribution of Raw Material**

The wide dispersal of raw material and their weak financial position necessitates that their small requirements of raw materials need to be made available at the needed time and close to their work place. It is suggested to set up raw material depots at suitable places to facilitate uninterrupted supply of standard raw material to the artisans in appropriate quantity and quality at reasonable rates. In such circumstance the state governments should supply raw material at cheaper rates which will encourage artisans to continue their production.

*** Product Diversification**

The artisan workers usually produce traditional utilitarian articles. Apart from these, non-traditional articles should be produced after examining the consumers preference and marketing orientation. The sector offers a great scope offers a great scope for the production of variety of artistic items if skill is slightly upgraded.

*** Modernizations of Production Technology**

To increase productivity and efficiency of the production system modernization of production technology is one of the basic perquisite. Every endeavor should be made to induce the workers to shift over to better tools and equipment which will help in eliminating long strenuous hours of work and low productivity.

*** Marketing Support**

A good market for the products household industries is important to promote the well being of the artisan workers or small entrepreneurs (Rao, 1989). Marketing support can be given to workers group through institutional arrangements or departmental support, an organization be setup which should be a no-profit no-loss body and should operate through hierarchical distribution collection centers.

*** Skill formation and Training**

For meeting the demand of better skill, which is a prerequisite for modernization of production technology it is recommended to improve skill of the artisan workers through training and

education of the workers in the related field. Managerial training should also be introduced for the management of the individual household units and cooperatives. This will widen the artisan workers outlook, make them realize the necessity of basic plans on the factual data and thus promotes the understanding of the principals and advantages of industrial.

*** Finance mobilization**

Inadequate finance has been one of the most important problems of the household industries and therefore, requires credit facilities and financial support for the purchase of raw materials, payments of wages and for meeting their business obligations. Along with the state governments, nationalized commercial banks and other financial organizations should come forward to finance the entrepreneurs providing short, medium and long term loans. Further it is suggested that finance should also be made available through post office. Proper step should be taken to popularize loan scheme.

*** Extension of employment opportunities during slack seasons**

It has been observed that during the slack season, the artisans are without continuous employment. It is suggested that state government emporium and co-operative marketing agencies should procure decorative items for their stock which can be produced during the slack season so as provide regular employment to the artisans.

*** Formation of co-operative societies**

There is an immediate need for the organization of cooperative societies on the sound footing so that they lead in the manufacture of quality and standard products. Cooperative societies should be established to give a lead in the manufacture of the quality and standard products. Such societies can make the artisans of the study area cooperative minded. These cooperative societies should take up a supply of raw material, purchase of finished goods from artisans, marketing and provision of credit. For this purpose, the cooperative societies should be given adequate financial assistance by the state governmental measures such as usual facilities of loan, grants, subsidies, marketing, mechanization and equitable distribution of products can be effectively channeled.

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